

Paper 9

**A STUDY ON INTERACTIVE RELATIONSHIP AMONG GENERAL INTELLIGENCE,
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, AND SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL STUDENTS OF THRISSUR DISTRICT IN KERALA**

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ABSTRACT

The present study titled ‘A study on interactive relationship among General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students of Thrissur district in Kerala’. The purpose of this study are a) to study the extent of General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students, b) to study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence, and Emotional Intelligence when Spiritual Intelligence is kept constant, c) to study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence, when Emotional Intelligence is kept constant, d) to study the extent of relationship among Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence when General Intelligence is kept constant. A sample was 400 students of standard nine of Thrissur District by stratified random sampling method. A standardized test to measure the General Intelligence by Dr Ahuja, Emotional Intelligence scale developed by Anukool Hyde, and Spiritual Intelligence test constructed by researcher were used. The results of this study revealed that a) The General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of students of standard nine of Thrissur district is average, b) Boys and Girls of standard nine of Thrissur district do not differ in their General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence, c) Urban school students of standard nine of Thrissur district are significantly higher in General Intelligence than that of Rural school students, d) Private school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is significantly higher in their General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence as well as in Spiritual Intelligence than that of Government school students, e) The Emotional Intelligence of students of standard nine of Thrissur district is above average, f) Urban school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is significantly higher in Emotional Intelligence than that of Rural school students, g) There is a negative low relationship among General Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine, h) There is a positive relationship among Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Thrissur district, i) There is a high positive

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relationship among General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Thrissur district. **Key words:** General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence, Spiritual Intelligence, Secondary students, Locality, type of schools.

Introduction

Intelligence is innate natural power and makes the individual to face and solve the complicated and difficult problems and situations. Our education system ends only at the development of cognitive aspects; there is no appropriate effort and preparation at the primary level for the development of emotional and spiritual intelligence. Today psychologist and educationists realized the fact that only concentrating on cognitive development will not help to be successful in life. The concept of intelligence has undergone immense changes and present day psychologist take pride in emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence. General intelligence, emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence holistically explain the full complexity of Intelligence. Thus, multiple ability of people was represented in terms of IQ, EQ and SQ.

Need for the study

The international document on learning the treasure within emphasizes the following four aspects as the focuses of education in 21st century.

‘Learning to do; Learning to live; Learning to learn and; Learning to live with others;’

-UNESCO Commission

To achieve this we need a resourceful, dynamic and goal oriented educational system. But the present education system aims only at preparing students for examinations rather than life. Seldom efforts have been made to develop individual in different aspects. All-round development has become a cliché in the context of present education.

Even now the concept of intelligence is the bases of success for everybody. It has been proved that many times even the persons with high intelligence fail in life. Expressing emotions in the appropriate manner is an art. It is the prime duty of the teachers and parents to train children, when they have difficulty in expressing emotions. Researches proved that emotional intelligence considered a basic requirement for the effective use of IQ.

Spiritual Quotient is multidimensional with focus on ego. One who is able to handle ones ego, is able to inculcate the virtues of humility, gratitude and politeness to achieve spiritual success.

Education is the fertile area where there is great demand for the fictionalization of General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence. It makes possible for the students

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to enjoy their learning and to flourish with all their potentialities. It helps the individual to prove to be human in all aspects. Thus there is an intense need to be aware of these three aspects in order to lead, guide and understand the students in the right way at the right time. It is high time for teachers to realize these competencies and to develop them among their students. Attempts must be made to give awareness to teachers and efforts have to be made to strengthen them with these competencies. In this context it will be interesting and helpful to know the interactive relationship among General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence and the impact of variables such as Locality, Gender and type of schools on these three aspects of secondary students. Thus the present study is an attempt to investigate the interactive relationship among General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students.

Statement of the problem:

‘A study on interactive relationship among General Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary students of standard Ninth of Thrissur District in Kerala in relation to their Gender, Type and Locality of schools’.

Operational definitions of the term

General Intelligence

Intelligence is a general capacity of an individual consciously to adjust his thinking to new requirements. It is a general mental adaptability to new problems and conditions. In the present study, General Intelligence means the total score obtained by the student on Ahuja’s Group Test of General Intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence refers to the capability of a person to manage and control his or her emotions and possess the ability to control the emotions of others as well. In other words, they can influence the emotions of other people also.

In the present study emotional intelligence means the total score obtained by the student on emotional intelligence scale developed by Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Date and Upindar Dhar, published by Vedant Publishers.

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Spiritual intelligence

Spiritual Intelligence refers to the capacity of an individual to possess a socially relevant purpose in life by understanding ‘self’ and having a high degree of conscience, compassion and commitment to human values’.

In the present study spiritual intelligence means the total score obtained by the student on spiritual intelligence test constructed by the researcher.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the extent of General Intelligence of secondary school students
2. To study whether there is any significant difference in General Intelligence in terms of gender, locality and type of schools
3. To study the extent of Emotional Intelligence of secondary school students
4. To study whether there is any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence in terms of gender, locality and type of schools
5. To study the extent of Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students
6. To study whether there is any significant difference in Spiritual Intelligence in terms of gender, locality and type of schools
7. To study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence, and Emotional Intelligence when Spiritual Intelligence is kept constant.
8. To study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence, when Emotional Intelligence is kept constant
9. To study the extent of relationship among Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence when General Intelligence is kept constant.

Variables of the study

Three variables are used in the present study

Tools used in the study

Group test of General Intelligence (CGTI)

A standardized test to measure the intelligence of children come under 13-17 years prepared by Ahuja has been used.

Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Dathe and Upider Dhar and published by Vedant publications, Lucknow has been used.

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Spiritual Intelligence test constructed by the researcher to measure the spiritual intelligence of secondary students.

Population of the study

All the standard nine students who are studying in Thrissur district in Kerala who study state syllabus.

Sample of the study

The sample of the study consist of 400 students of standard nine, under the age of 14 years from the Thrissur district in Kerala who study Kerala state syllabus using stratified sampling technique.

Statistical techniques used

To analyse the objectives of the study descriptive statistics -Mean (M), S.D, Cumulative frequency percentage, Quartiles, Skewness and inferential statistics such as ‘t’ vaue, partial correlation ‘r’ was calculated.

Analysis and interpretation of objective one

The first objective was to find out the extent of General Intelligence of secondary school students of standard Nine.

Mean, Median, Standard Deviation (SD), Quartiles (Q1.Q2,Q3) and Skewness (Sk) were calculated for the distribution of scores on group test of General Intelligence.

Table 1.1 Mean, Median, Standard Deviation (SD), Quartiles (Q1.Q2,Q3) and Skewness (Sk) of the distribution of scores on group test of General Intelligence.

Total number of students	Total score	M	Mdn	SD	Q1	Q2	Q3	Sk
400	40	28.9	30	6.93	24	30	34	-0.4762

From table 1.1, it is clear that the mean lies between Q1 and Q2. Hence the performance of standard nine students of secondary schools of Thrissur district is average. The table shows that the mean is less than median. Hence, the distribution of the scores on group test of General Intelligence is negatively skewed. But this negligible degree of skewness shows that the distribution closely approaches the normal distribution.

Interpretation of results

1. The General Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is average.

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Analysis and interpretation of objective two

The second objective was to study whether there is any significant difference in General Intelligence in terms of gender, locality and type of schools

i) Analysis based on Gender

In order to check the significance of this difference a research hypothesis was formulated as: there is a significant difference between in General Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls.

Table 1.2: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of General Intelligence among Boys and Girls.

Variables	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Boys	200	40	28.23	6.54	0.1427	Not significant at 0.01 level
Girls	200	40	28.125	8.093		

From the above table 1.2, it is revealed that the formulated null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference in the general intelligence of Boys and Girls of standard Nine of secondary schools’ was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the General Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls of Thrissur district.

ii) Analysis based on Locality of schools

Table 1.3: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of General Intelligence in terms of Locality of schools.

Variables	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Urban	200	40	33.128	4.975	10.405	significant at 0.01 level
Rural	200	40	26.683	7.208		

From the above table 1.3, it is observed that Rural schools Mean is less than Urban schools Mean. Hence null hypothesis rejected. This shows that general intelligence of urban school students is significantly more than the Rural school students. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in General Intelligence of Urban school students and rural school students.

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iii) Analysis based on type of schools

Table 1.4: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of General Intelligence in terms of Type of schools.

Type of schools	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Private	200	40	31.326	4.401	5.329	significant at 0.01 level
Government	200	40	27.698	8.564		

From the above table 1.4, it is observed that Government schools Mean is less than Private schools Mean. Hence null hypothesis was rejected. This shows that General Intelligence of Private school students are significantly more than the Government school students. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in General Intelligence of Government school students and Private school students.

Analysis and interpretation of objective three

The third objective of the study was to find out the extent of Emotional Intelligence of Secondary school students of standard Nine.

Table 1.5 Mean, Median, Standard Deviation (SD), Quartiles (Q1,Q2,Q3) and Skewness (Sk) of the distribution of scores on group test of Emotional Intelligence.

Total number of students	Total score	M	Mdn	SD	Q1	Q2	Q3	Sk
400	150	93.52	93	11.44	86	93	101	0.1311

From table 1.5, it is clear that the mean lies between Q2 and Q3. So, the Emotional Intelligence of standard nine students of secondary schools of Thrissur district is above average. The table also reveals that the mean is slightly more than median. Hence, the distribution of the scores on Emotional Intelligence is positively skewed. But this negligible degree of skewness shows that the distribution closely approaches the normal distribution.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Four

The Fourth objective was to study whether there is any significant difference in Emotional Intelligence in terms of gender, locality and type of schools

i) Analysis based on Gender

In order to check the significance of this difference a research hypothesis was formulated as: there is a significant difference between in Emotional Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls.

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Table 1.6: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of Emotional Intelligence among Boys and Girls.

Variables	N	Max.score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Boys	200	150	90.295	10.645	0,0278	Not significant at 0.01 level
Girls	200	150	90.325	10.914		

From the above table it is revealed that the formulated null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of Boys and Girls of standard Nine of secondary schools’ was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls of Trissur district.

ii) Analysis based on Locality of schools

Table 1.7: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Locality of schools.

Locality	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Urban	200	150	98.505	10.659	7.0144	significant at 0.01 level
Rural	200	150	90.86	11.134		

From the above table 1.7, it is observed that rural schools Mean is less than urban schools Mean. Hence null hypothesis rejected. This shows that general intelligence of Urban school students is significantly more than the Rural school students. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Urban school students and Rural school students.

iii) Analysis based on type of schools

Table 1.8: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Type of schools.

Type of schools	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Private	200	150	95.53	10.598	3.099	significant at 0.01 level
Government	200	150	91.985	12.22		

From the above table 1.8, it is observed that mean score of Private school students is higher than Government schools. Hence null hypothesis was rejected. This shows that Emotional Intelligence of Private school students is significantly more than the Government school students. Thus, it can

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be concluded that there is a significant difference in Emotional Intelligence of Government school students and Private school students.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Five

The Fifth objective of the study was to find out the extent of Spiritual Intelligence of Secondary school students of standard Nine.

Table 1.9: Mean, Median, Standard Deviation (SD), Quartiles (Q1.Q2, Q3) and Skewness (Sk) of the distribution of scores on group test of Spiritual Intelligence.

Total number of students	Total score	M	Mdn	SD	Q1	Q2	Q3	Sk
400	50	31.1	32	5.61	28	32	35	-0.48128

From table 1.9, it is clear that the mean lies between Q1 and Q2 and it shows that the Spiritual Intelligence of Secondary students of standard Nine of Thrissur District is Average. The table also reveals that the mean is less than median. SO, the distribution of the scores on Spiritual Intelligence test is negatively skewed. But this negligible degree of skewness shows that the distribution closely approaches the normal distribution.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Six

The Sixth objective was to study whether there is any significant difference in Spiritual Intelligence in terms of Gender, Locality and Type of schools

i) Analysis based on Gender

In order to check the significance of this difference a research hypothesis was formulated as: there is a significant difference between in Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls.

Table 1.10: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of Spiritual Intelligence among Boys and Girls.

Variables	N	Max. score	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Boys	200	50	30.7	5.3125	1.386	Not significant at 0.01 level
Girls	200	50	31.47	5.7855		

From the above table 1.10, it is revealed that the null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference in the Spiritual Intelligence of Boys and Girls of standard Nine of secondary schools’ was accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the Spiritual

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Intelligence of secondary school Boys and Girls of Thrissur district.

ii) Analysis based on Locality

Table 1.11: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Spiritual Intelligence Test in terms of Locality of schools.

Locality	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Urban	200	30.9	5.4024	0.25	Not significant at 0.01 level
Rural	200	31.04	5.791		

From the above table 1.11, it is observed that the difference between the mean scores of Urban and Rural school students is very low. Hence the null hypothesis accepted. This shows that there is no significant difference in the scores of Spiritual Intelligence among Urban school students and Rural school students.

iii) Analysis based on type of schools

Table 1.12: number (N), Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the scores on Group test of Emotional Intelligence in terms of Type of schools.

Type of schools	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remarks
Government	200	28.665	5.5367	5.832	significant at 0.01 level
Private	200	31.785	5.1567		

From the above table 1.12, it is observed that Government schools Mean is less than Private schools Mean. Hence null hypothesis was rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the scores of Spiritual Intelligence among Government and Private school students of Standard Nine.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Eight

The eighth objective of the study was to study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence and Emotional intelligence of standard nine students when spiritual intelligence is kept constant. In order to find out the extent of relationship the data has been analyzed and interpreted using partial correlation ‘r’.

Table 1.13: Partial correlation of the Scores of General Intelligence and Emotional intelligence when spiritual intelligence is constant

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Variables	N	M	SD	‘r’	Partial correlation	Result
GI	400	28.9	6.93	0.95	r 12.3 = - 0.01	Not significant at 0.01 level
EI	400	93.5	11.44			
SI (partial out)	400	31.1	5.61			

From the table 1.13, it is clear that there is low negative relationship between General Intelligence and Emotional intelligence of standard nine students when Spiritual Intelligence is kept constant. Therefore, null hypothesis accepted and concluded that there is a negative relationship between these two variables.

The analysis of data revealed that there is no significant relationship between General Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence. The present study showed a low negative relationship between two variables namely General Intelligence and Emotional intelligence. i.e as the General Intelligence increased the Emotional Intelligence decreased. This is a drastic fact, which needs immediate attention from the education sector. Today’s education as it aims only on the intellectual development of students, the teachers forget about the most important area of Emotional Intelligence, which makes a person stressful in life. The current events show that the present generation becomes very low in emotional intelligence as a result man becomes mere animal. To have change to this situation the present education system should concentrate on developing Emotional Intelligence is students. For this object special arrangements should be done in the curriculum and immediate actions should be taken from the authorities.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Nine

The Ninth objective of the study was to study the extent of relationship among General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of standard nine students when Emotional Intelligence is kept constant. In order to find out the extent of relationship the data has been analyzed and interpreted using partial correlation ‘r’.

Table 1.14: Partial correlation of the Scores of General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence when Emotional Intelligence is constant

Variables	N	M	SD	‘r’	Partial correlation	Result
GI	400	28.9	6.93	0.99	r 13.2 = 0.89	significant at 0.01 level
SI	400	31.1	5.61			
EI (partial out)	400	93.5	11.44			

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From the table 1.14, it is clear that there is high positive relationship between General Intelligence and Spiritual intelligence of standard nine students when Emotional Intelligence is kept constant. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that there is a significant relationship between General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of standard nine students when Emotional Intelligence is kept constant.

So far intelligence was considered to be innate and cannot be increased beyond a limit set by heredity. But the result of this study points out that since General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence are positively related by using techniques to increase we can develop General Intelligence too.

Analysis and interpretation of objective Ten

The Tenth objective of the study was to study the extent of relationship among Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of standard nine students when General Intelligence is kept constant. In order to find out the extent of relationship the data has been analyzed and interpreted using partial correlation ‘r’.

Table 1.15: Partial correlation of the Scores of Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence when General Intelligence is constant

Variables	N	M	SD	‘r’	Partial correlation	Result
EI	400	93.5	11.44	0.99	$r_{23.1} = 0.44$	significant at 0.01 level
SI	400	31.1	5.61			
GI (partial out)	400	28.9	6.93			

From the table 1.15, it is clear that $r_{23.1}$ value between EI and SI when GI is constant is positive and significant at 0.01 level. In the light of this it could be interpreted that there is a positive moderate relationship among EI and SI when GI is kept constant. Therefore, null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that there is a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of standard nine students when General Intelligence is kept constant.

When one acts from a high emotional maturity and intelligence, spirituality comes spontaneously. Based on this view the result can be interpreted that as Emotional Intelligence increases Spiritual Intelligence also increases.

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Major findings of the study

1. The General Intelligence of students of standard nine of Thrissur district is average.
2. Boys and Girls of standard nine of Thrissur district do not differ in their General Intelligence.
3. Urban school students of standard nine of Thrissur district are significantly higher in General Intelligence than that of Rural school students.
4. Private school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is significantly higher in their General Intelligence than that of Government school students.
5. The Emotional Intelligence of students of standard nine of Thrissur district is above average.
6. Boys and Girls of standard nine of Thrissur district do not differ in their Emotional Intelligence.
7. Urban school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is significantly higher in Emotional Intelligence than that of Rural school students.
8. Private school students of standard nine of Thrissur district is significantly higher in their Emotional Intelligence than that of Government school students.
9. The Spiritual Intelligence of students of standard nine of Thrissur district is average.
10. Boys and Girls of standard nine of Thrissur district do not differ in their Spiritual Intelligence.
11. Urban and Rural of standard nine of Thrissur district do not differ in their Spiritual Intelligence.
12. Spiritual Intelligence of Private school students are higher than that of government school students.
13. There is a negative low relationship among General Intelligence and Emotional Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Trissur district.
14. There is a positive relationship among Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Trissur district.
15. There is a high positive relationship among General Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence of secondary school students of standard nine of Trissur district.

Educational Implications of the study

1. Teachers may be trained to opt different effective techniques and methods of value orientation
2. More and more scope is to be provided to develop emotional and spiritual intelligence
3. Counseling and guidance centre in each school is to be organized and each child is oriented personally to improve him/herself.
4. Workshops and guidance trainings for teachers, parents and students may be arranged.
5. Encourage students to build good rapport with each other.

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6. Teachers may guide students to express their emotions in a proper way.
7. Students are to be taught to control their mind and senses.
8. Practicing techniques to develop emotional and spiritual intelligence among the students isto be included in the Teacher education curriculum.
9. Include yoga, meditation, music, and art in education system.
10. Encourage community based activities like Scouts, clubs, parent –teacher association etc
11. Through appropriate guidance develop in children purify of thoughts, speech and action, passion for knowledge.
12. Restructure our examination by including weightage for emotional and spiritual intelligence domains.

Suggestion for further research

1. A comparative stud on GI, EI and SI of different professional students.
2. Effect of specially designed instructional material for developing emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence of students.
3. Similar studies with other covariates like study habit, adjustment, personality, interest, attitude can be done.
4. Effect of yoga and meditation in developing of emotional and spiritual intelligence.
5. GI, EI, and SI of slum or tribe students can be done.

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